

The effects of CNT type, alignment and dopants on piezoresistance in CNT fibres

Anastasiia Mikhalchan,^a Ángel Víctor Labordet Álvarez,^a Moisés Zarzoso,^{a,b} Carlos González,^{a,b*} Juan J. Vilatela^{a*}

^a IMDEA Materials Institute, 28906 Getafe, Madrid, Spain

^b Universidad Politécnica de Madrid, E.T.S. de Ingenieros de Caminos, 28040 Madrid, Spain

* Corresponding author. IMDEA Materials Institute, 28906 Getafe, Madrid, Spain

E-mail address: juanjose.vilatela@imdea.org (J. J. Vilatela), Carlos Gonzalez carlosdaniel.gonzalez@imdea.org

ABSTRACT

Carbon nanotube fibres (CNTF) are piezoresistive, hence heralded as deformation sensors in applications ranging from flexible touch sensors to artificial skins and robotics. This work studies the piezoresistive behaviour of a wide range of CNT fibres from different sources, processing routes and microstructures. It provides a unifying view of the factors controlling piezoresistance in CNT fibres and related nanocarbon networks. We clarify the role of alignment and concentration of dopants and the constituent CNT type, demonstrating that the origin of piezoresistance in aligned fibres is the direct deformation of the constituent nanotubes, therefore, it is governed by the bulk modulus and thus the degree of CNT alignment. Doping through intercalation, which does not affect modulus or CNT separation, is detrimental to piezoresistive sensing, reducing the gauge factor proportionally to its decrease in resistivity. Aligned fibres show a quasi-linear piezoresistive response, with a positive change in resistance for all deformation modes applied: axial tension, axial or transverse compression. The axial gauge factor is shown to be proportional to fibre Young's modulus, with values of 2-9 for fibres spun from aerogels and above 30 for undoped fibres spun from liquid crystal solutions, respectively. Piezoresistance is attributed to the formation of internal barriers for conduction between metallic regions, which arise from the heterogeneous stress distribution along individual CNTs inherent in shear lag-type stress transfer. Commercial multifilament CNT yarns with a high degree of alignment and a format amenable for integration in large structures have demonstrated the piezoresistive gauge factors of 4 and sufficient sensitivity at strains below 1% suitable for structural health monitoring of engineering structural composites.

Keywords: CNT fibres, piezoresistive sensors, gauge factor, structural composites

1. INTRODUCTION

Nanocarbons are excellent building blocks for piezoresistive strain sensors. Piezoresistive properties of elastomeric matrices filled with carbon black fillers have been studied since the 90s [1–3]. The advent of high aspect ratio nanocarbons, namely carbon nanotubes (CNT) and graphene, enabled the fabrication of nanocomposites with high piezoresistive sensitivity [4–7]. Gauge factors (GF) as high as several hundred have been shown for the CNT-filled elastomeric polymers [8,9] and non-polymeric materials, such as cementitious composites, used for self-sensing multifunctional civil infrastructure [10]. Their piezoresistive sensitivity is significantly higher than the conventional constantan alloy Cu/Ni (GF of 2) used in strain gauges or fibre optics sensors (GF of 1).

One of the most important macroscopic formats of nanocarbon is aligned fibres [11]. CNT fibres are finished components with well-defined macroscopic properties and have an ideal geometry for sensing, for example, in smart textiles [12], human movement analysis [13], artificial neuromuscular [14] and energy harvesting materials [15,16]. Their high stiffness, linear-elastic behaviour at small deformations and high damage tolerance [17] are in the range of high-performance reinforcement fibres and make them attractive for high-end structural composites [18,19]. Structural health monitoring (SHM) of aerospace-grade composites is challenging, and aircraft manufacturers are constantly searching for novel solutions for sensing strains under 1% [20,21]. For these applications, continuous CNT fibres are excellent candidates for sensor development [22] due to their light weight, flexibility and, in addition, compatibility with novel composite manufacturing techniques, such as fused filament fabrication [23–25]. Indeed, NASA has intensely explored CNT fibres as printable structural sensors [26]. More recently, a European consortium¹ demonstrated printable CNT yarn-based sensors fully integrated into a thermoplastic CFRP laminate with a piezoresistive gauge factor of 12 at 0.2% strain [27].

Yet, despite progress on the application of CNT fibres for SHM, the parameters that govern the bulk piezoresistivity of CNT fibres at the macroscale are still poorly understood. Several studies have separately measured the piezoresistive properties of different types of CNT fibres. Twisted fibres or yarns spun from CNT arrays [28] showed a range of piezoresistive gauge factors between 0.2 – 0.5 at strain under 1% [29,30] and 1-2 at 0.25% strain [31]. CNT fibres spun from aerogels directly from the gas phase, which have similar CNT polydispersity but a higher degree of alignment, have also been studied. Piezoresistivity in these aligned fibres is proportional to fibre

¹ DOMMINIO: Digital method for improved manufacturing of next-generation multifunctional airframe parts: a step closer to cost-effective, efficient, and sustainable manufacturing <https://domminioproject.eu/>

stress, with a gauge factor up to 12 (maximum measured 15) when measured at strains above 1%, thus beyond the elastic regime [32]. Their gauge factor is preserved under cycling loading, although with evidence of hysteresis and creep [32].

These properties contrast with the current understanding of the piezoresistance of nanocarbon networks of CNTs or graphene randomly dispersed in polymer matrices at low volume fractions. The electrical properties of such nanocomposites follow percolation behaviour, and their piezoresistance stems mainly from the changes in junction resistance produced upon breaking and re-forming of nanocarbon junctions during straining [33]. Hence, their resistance changes following applied *strain*, with gauge factors reaching 500 in tension [34] and negative gauge factors and saturated sensitivity in compression [35,36].

In this work, we analyse various laboratory-grade and commercial CNT fibres and multifilament yarns produced using different spinning methods to determine the effect of alignment, CNT molecular composition, and the presence of dopant(s) on their piezoresistive strain sensing capabilities. We demonstrate that the origin of piezoresistance in aligned CNT fibres is the direct deformation of the constituent nanotubes, with a positive change in resistance observed for all deformation modes applied and tensile GF proportional to the fibre's Herman's orientation factor. Surprisingly, doping through intercalation reduces the gauge factor proportionally to the decrease in resistivity. In addition, we show that commercial multifilament CNT yarns (tows of multiple CNT filaments) have good sensitivity under 1% strain, suitable for sensor development for strain monitoring of structural composites.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Materials

CNT fibres were produced at IMDEA Materials Institute using the floating catalyst (FCCVD) method in the vertical tubular reactor at 1300 °C. Toluene and butanol were used as carbon sources, ferrocene as catalyst source, and thiophene as a sulfur promoter for the reaction as described elsewhere [37] to produce fibres of different molecular compositions.—Specifically, fibres were produced with predominant populations of few- or multi-layer CNTs with a number of layers between 2 and 10 and mean length under 40 µm determined by TEM analysis as a ratio of the total length of CNT observed over the number of CNT ends [38]. However, individual single- and few-layer CNT are flexible and usually bundled, so they might be sufficiently longer than 40 µm. The spun aerogel filaments were densified with a solvent (isopropanol) and then dried overnight. A few metres of CNT fibres of each type were collected, with diameters ranging from 10 to 50 µm for performing the mechanical and structural characterisation. Commercial CNT

fibres spun from liquid crystalline (LC) solutions with different diameters (20, 40, and 100 μm) and degrees of alignment served as comparators (Dexmat, USA). The LC-spinning does not involve the usage of either a binder or a polymer, but the resultant fibres may contain residual acid traces. Such CNT fibres are known for their compacted structure with minimized porosity, as reported elsewhere [39].

Three commercial CNT yarns, composed of multiple CNT fibre filaments, were used: Yarn#1 (Tortech Nanofibers, Israel) and Yarn#2 (Huntsman, USA), spun from aerogels, and Yarn#3 (Dexmat, USA) spun from liquid crystalline solution. A 6-tow (6-ply) Yarn#1 was comprised of predominantly multi-layer CNT [40] with a low twist of 429 twists per metre (TPM) at 10-16 ° surface twist angle, *Supplementary Information S1*). Yarn#2 was untwisted, with undisclosed molecular composition. Yarn#3 was spun of predominant single-layer CNT, with a 10° surface twist angle and 2500 TPM. In order to investigate the behaviour of CNT fibres under compressive loading, a thin tow of 10 aerogel filaments was produced at IMDEA Materials Institute. For this, the winder turned 10 times (10 rotations of the collecting bobbin), and the CNT aerogel filaments overlapped and merged into a thin yarn, which was densified off-line with acetone and left to dry overnight. After drying, the yarn was peeled off the bobbin, ready for handling and analysis. The tow was embedded in an S2 woven glass fibre reinforced (GFRP) laminate with epoxy matrix, consisting of 4 glass fibre plies, cured for 2 hours at 180 °C in a vacuum bag (ramp at 3°C/min from 30 to 180 °C, followed by an isothermal cure for 2h at 180 °C). To make the electrical contacts with the CNT tow, the conductive epoxy paste was first applied to its ends and cured before the glass fibre laminate resin infusion. The embedded contacts provided low contact resistance and demonstrated stability during the resin infusion and subsequent curing of GFRP.

2.2 Methods

To measure the resistance of individual CNT fibres and multi-filament yarns, indium-based solder was used due to stable results with low contact resistance. The contact resistance was characterized by 2-probe measurements following the Transfer Length Measurement (TLM) method [41]. The TLM setup consisted of a CNT fibre or yarn placed on the individual glass slides, avoiding additional pretension. Six to seven equally spaced contacts were made on each fibre at equal spacing. The resistance in the contact area (R_c^{Total}) was obtained as the Y-intercept of the linear approximation (the least square fit) of the data (*Supplementary Information, S2*). Manufacturing the GFRP laminate with fully-embedded electrical contacts required the high-temperature curing of an aerospace-grade epoxy resin at 180 °C, invalidating indium as a material

for the electrical contacts due to its lower melting point (156.6 °C). Therefore, the conductive epoxy paste was used, and the TLM measurements were performed after curing the epoxy paste at 180 °C for 3 h.

The exemplary individual CNT fibres were measured using the 2-probe and 4-probe techniques (*Supplementary Information, S3*), testifying the acceptable level of contact resistance when compared to the initial resistance (R_0) of the fibres (*Supplementary Information, S4*). The current-voltage characteristics of the samples (CNT fibre yarns in dry-state and fully embedded in the GFRP laminate) were recorded up to 5V (yarn) and up to 24 V (laminate) and confirm the Ohmic nature of the contacts between the metal wires and CNT materials. The durability of the electrical contacts was retained for a period of over 24 months, as the stability of the fully embedded contacts was later confirmed in the unloaded and loaded states (*Supplementary Information, S5, S6, S7*).

In-situ mechanical tensile tests of individual CNT fibres coupled with piezoresistive measurements were performed using a FAVIMAT tensile testing machine (Textechno) with a load cell of 2 N at the gauge length of 2 cm, using modified clamps combined with indium-soldered electrical contacts. Macroscopic commercial CNT yarns were tested at the gauge length of 5 cm using an Instron tensile testing machine equipped with a load cell of 500 N. The CNT yarns were fixed between tabs, and the electrical contacts were prepared outside the tabs by mechanical crimping combined with Sn-soldering to the wires to minimise contact resistance. The samples were subjected to the cycling tensile tests in a quasi-static regime at 1 mm/min speed. The electrical resistance was recorded every 0.12 s using a KEITHLEY 2450 Source Meter with measurements configured with KickStart software. Prior to the cycling tests, the resistance of CNT yarn samples was monitored for a few minutes to check the stability of the electrical connections and any potential resistance variation.

The SEM images of the CNT fibres were taken using the FIB-FEG SEM Helios Nanolab 600i (FEI) microscope; twist angles were measured using optical microscopy and Fiji, an open-source image processing package based on ImageJ2 software.

SAXS analysis of individual CNT fibres was done at the NCD-SWEET beamline at ALBA synchrotron (Barcelona, Spain) with radiation wavelength 1 Å in the q-range of 0.0015-0.25 Å⁻¹ using a microfocus beam with a spot size of approximately 10 µm. Sample-to-detector distance and other parameters were calibrated using reference materials, and data were processed with the DAWN software [42]. The SAXS patterns of commercial CNT yarns were collected at IMDEA using SAXSpoint 5.0 laboratory beamline (Anton Paar, Austria), equipped with Primux 100 microfocus X-ray source (Cu), patterns were corrected for the transmittance and background using SAXSanalysis software (V 4.20). The intensity profiles were obtained after radial integration for

the q range 0.07-0.08 \AA^{-1} , subtracted background and fitted to a Pseudo Voigt 1 function, as described in [43,44].

Three-point bend (TPB) tests were done on the GFRP coupon of 1.14 mm thickness, 110 mm length, 30 mm width, at the support length of 96 mm, crosshead rate of 2 mm/s, till reaching the maximum load of 300 N. The specimen's dimensions were set due to the availability of the materials, focusing on the analysis of the electrical behaviour of the CNT yarn in a fully embedded state, not on the flexural properties of the GFRP laminate. The span-to-thickness ratio (84:1) was higher than the requirements of ASTM D7264 standard (32:1) but acceptable for bending highly orthotropic laminates, with the specimen length of 15% longer than the support span. The CNT tow was positioned between the 3rd and 4th plies, out of the normal plane, to enable us to track either tensile or compressive deformations by flipping the coupon in three-point bend tests.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Piezoresistive behaviour of individual CNT fibres under tensile and compressive deformations

The schematic view of the experimental setup used for the piezoresistive analysis of individual CNT fibres under tensile deformations is presented in *Supplementary Information, S8*. Two contact points of soldering material were first attached to each CNT fibre; those points were then gripped between an indium foil attached to the clamps of the tensile tester. The mechanical performance of CNT fibres was investigated, and the cycling tests were performed to characterise the piezoresistive behaviour. The cyclability, hysteresis and stability of the electrical measurements were evaluated in ten tensile loading-unloading cycles. The tensile modulus was determined in the elastic regime (typically, under 1% strain). The piezoresistive gauge factor was calculated as a slope of the linear regression over the loading part of the stress-strain curves in the cycling tests as a ratio of the relative change in electrical resistance ($\Delta R/R_0$) to the mechanical strain (ϵ). Figure 1 presents examples of the stress-strain curve, tensile cycling loading and longitudinal resistance data for a CNT fibre produced from aerogel spinning at IMDEA (see *Supplementary Information, S9* for the corresponding plots for a highly-aligned LC-spun CNT fibre).

Figure 1. Example of tensile and piezoresistive data for a CNT fibre spun from aerogel, IMDEA Materials. A) stress-strain curve showing features of elasto-plastic behaviour with a region of elastic deformation below 1% (shown with a linear fit) and following transition to the plastic zone; and B) tensile cycles up to 0.5% strain with notable hardening of the CNT network structure, with corresponding C) change in resistance following applied tensile strain and D) quasi-linear piezoresistive response.

The stress-strain plot in Fig. 2B reveals a slight drift to higher strains on repeated tensile cycles due to the presence of non-recoverable deformation. Evaluated as a strain difference between the peak load of the first and subsequent hysteresis loops, it may represent the relative creep accumulating during each cycle [45]. A higher level of non-recoverable deformation was observed for FCCVD-spun CNT fibres in comparison to highly-aligned LC-spun ones, ascribed to their porous network structure that rearranges under the tensile loading (*Supplementary Information, S10*). After the first few cycles, their structure reaches a balance, as can be assessed through the minute modulus change at the following loadings (*Supplementary Information, S10*), and the fibres remain well in the elastic regime at this low strain range (<0.5%). Stress relaxation behaviour and creep are typical of CNT fibres [32].

The electrical resistance of the CNT fibres changed significantly upon axial stretching following the loading-unloading cycles. In the elastic regime, the change in resistance was quasi-linear with applied tensile strain and stress throughout the loading and unloading segments

(*Supplementary Information, S11*). A hysteresis in the resistance was observed for all CNT fibres for each full cycle, defined as the ratio (absolute value) of the area within the hysteresis loop between loading and unloading segments [33,46]. After the first loading cycle, the relatively high hysteresis decreased and stabilized at the level of 15% and 5% for the FCCVD- and LC-spun CNT fibres, correspondingly (*Supplementary Information, S12*). The measured resistance exhibited excellent repeatability and consistency in response at each cycle, as evident by the nearly constant relative change in resistance ($\Delta R/R_0$), with no statistically significant changes in ten cycles (no outliers outside 1.5 times the interquartile range were observed under loading and unloading segments) (*Supplementary Information, S13*).

We performed tests under axial and transverse compression to gain more insights into their piezoresistive behaviour (Figure 2). Axial compression was applied through three-point bending (TPB) tests of a non-symmetric GFRP coupon with an embedded CNT tow. For this, a CNT tow consisting of 10 individual aerogel-spun CNT filaments was embedded into the GFRP layup before resin infusion and subsequent curing. The CNT tow was placed away from the neutral plane, enabling recording of the change in resistance in response to either tensile (when the CNT tow was positioned closer to the bottom side) or compressive (when the CNT tow was closer to the top side) deformations by flipping the same coupon. The tow was used in this test because it is generally very hard to embed an individual CNT fibre with a typical diameter of $<20 \mu\text{m}$ into the laminate following the standard layup and resin infusion process, and moreover, to prepare and preserve the stable electrical contacts with a single CNT fibre filament. In this study, the electrical contacts between the CNT tow and the electrical cables were made prior to the resin infusion and curing, so they were fully incorporated into the GFRP laminate to ensure stability after curing and in testing.

Figure 2B shows the similar positive resistance change observed under tensile and compressive deformations plotted in the same graph. Note that as strain is represented by a positive or negative sign for tensile and compressive deformations, the piezoresistive strain sensitivity (gauge factor) is negative when calculated for the compressive part [47]. The CNT tow has demonstrated high strain sensitivity with the GF of -39.2 for compressive strain up to 0.4%, and 45.1 for tensile deformation within 0.2-0.4% strain range. To compare, the CNT yarn dry-spun from a CVD array embedded in epoxy resin has shown the negative change in resistance in compression with GF of 29.3 and 21.2 under tensile and compressive deformations up to 0.1% strain, respectively [48].

Figure 2. A) A thin tow of 10 CNT fibres embedded into the GFRP laminate coupon subjected to three-point bend test, B) change in resistance occurred in response to tensile and compressive deformations of GFRP with linear fitting and similar piezoresistive sensitivity in both deformation modes, C, D) notable change in resistance observed in individual highly-aligned CNT fibres produced by LC spinning under transverse compression test.

Similarly, in a simpler test, transverse compression was induced by resting a known weight of 20 and 50 grams onto a CNT fibre while its longitudinal conductivity was recorded (Figure 2C,D). This also increased relative resistance, which augmented under larger compressive stress experienced by a CNT fibre of known diameter (3.14×10^{-4} MPa and 7.85×10^{-4} MPa, correspondingly).

The tensile and compressive results confirm that CNT fibres have a positive change in resistance under both deformation modes for relatively small deformations in the elastic regime. This behaviour contrasts with that of nanocomposites with dispersed nanofillers. The nanocomposite network of conductive fillers produces a negative change in resistance (decrease in resistance) under tensile loading above elastic regime (strains higher than 2%) due to a densification of the network, and therefore, reduction in interparticle contact distances and junction resistance [5]. Also, ceramic-based composites show a negative change in resistance under compressive deformation [49].

3.2 Piezoresistive properties of CNT fibres spun from aerogels and liquid crystalline solutions

The effect of CNT alignment on the piezoresistive behaviour

Several CNT fibres were evaluated to corroborate the effect of CNT alignment on their piezoresistive properties. First, the CNT fibres were produced at IMDEA from aerogels at different spinning conditions, which led to a range of samples with different degrees of CNT alignment.

Second, several commercial fibres of various diameters and degrees of alignment spun from liquid crystalline solutions of SWCNTs and DWSNTs in superacids were tested as comparators. These fibres were free from dopants to eliminate their strong effect on piezoresistance, as discussed later in the paper.

Figure 3 shows electron micrographs and 2D SAXS patterns recorded for the samples in this study: the fibres produced by FCCVD (Figure 3A) and LC (Figure 3B). They evidence significant differences in the degree of CNT alignment.

Figure 3. SEM images of individual A) exemplary aerogel-spun CNT fibre (diameter $\sim 15 \mu\text{m}$), comprised of an interconnected network of CNT bundles with preferential alignment and fibrillar morphology; B) well-aligned LC-spun CNT fibre with a compacted less porous structure (diameter $20 \mu\text{m}$); with corresponding SAXS patterns presented in inserts.

We measured the piezoresistive behaviour and extracted their GF to understand the structural factors controlling piezoresistance. As shown in Figure 4A, the GF increases with increasing fibre modulus. This trend is observed for both LC-spun and FCCVD-spun fibres, although, it is much more pronounced for the former ones. The GF reaches a value of 30, which is significantly above previous reports on continuous CNT fibres. The data also suggest that annealed CNT fibres of higher modulus should reach GF above ~ 100 [50]. It has been previously shown that fibre modulus is controlled by the degree of CNT alignment; hence, it is expected to strongly affect GF. This is, indeed, the case, as shown in Figure 4B, which represents GF against fibre Herman's orientation factor. This orientation factor commonly used for fibrous structures takes values of 0 for random alignment, -0.5 for perfect perpendicular alignment, and 1 for perfect parallel alignment. Alternatively, using the uniform stress model, the GF and alignment can be directly related by:

$$GF = aE = a \left(\frac{1}{e_{CNT}} + \frac{\langle \cos^2 \theta \rangle}{g_{CNT}} \right)^{-1},$$

where a is a sensitivity factor, e_{CNT} and g_{CNT} are the bundle axial and shear moduli, respectively, and $\langle \cos^2\theta \rangle$ is an orientation parameter related to the distribution of CNTs normal angles to the fibre axis (θ), which can be calculated from the SAXS equatorial intensity distribution. Definitions of $\langle \cos^2\theta \rangle$ and the Herman's orientation $\langle P_2 \rangle$ factor are included in *Supplementary Information, S14*.

The sensitivity factor enables the comparison of fibres of different compositions, adjusting for their different moduli. Thus, the data in Figure 4A confirm that the sensitivity factor a is higher for the LC-spun than for FCCVD-synthesized CNT fibres. This is likely due to differences in the type of constituent CNTs. Figure 4C compares the diameter distributions of CNTs for the different materials tested. The narrow diameter distributions of either SWCNTs or DWCNTs used in spinning the CNT fibres from liquid crystalline solutions give a high sensitivity (sensitivity factor a of 0.17-0.22 for undoped fibres). The broader diameter distribution for FCCVD-synthesized CNT fibres results in a sensitivity factor a below 0.1 (0.02-0.10).

Figure 4. The relationships between the piezoresistive CNT fibres GF with A) the elastic modulus (as a reference of internal CNT alignment) and B) the orientation parameter $\langle P_2 \rangle$ determined from SAXS profiles revealing higher piezoresistive sensitivity for fibres with higher CNT alignment;

C) Comparison of the outer diameter distributions for FCCVD-synthesized and LC-spun CNT fibres. Legend includes the average number of CNT layers (n).

The effect of dopants on the piezoresistive behaviour of CNT fibres

It was initially expected that the CNT fibres with well-packed and less porous structure with higher mechanical properties would have higher piezoresistive sensitivity. However, the as-produced benchmark LC-spun fibres (supplied without additional post-spinning treatment) show noisy electrical signals when stretched to 1%, with a gauge factor of only ~ 1 -1.5. This low gauge factor is, in fact, caused by doping from the residual CSA purposely trapped in the aligned CNT bundles at production. It is known that the residual CSA dopant in LC-spun fibres increases the electrical conductivity to an impressive $\sim 10^7$ S/m and, once removed by high-temperature annealing, results in a $\sim 40\%$ drop in the electrical conductivity [51]. Our experiments revealed a notable increase in the piezoresistive gauge factor of the LC-spun CNT fibres when a substantial amount of residual acid doping was removed by annealing at 400-500 °C (Figure 5). The fully undoped (through annealing at 1400 °C [50]) LC-spun CNT fibres showed an average gauge factor as high as 26 (maximum measured value 31 for a fibre spun from DWCNT), with some reduction in their electrical conductance.

A similar negative effect of doping on piezoresistivity was noted when testing the aligned LC-spun CNT fibres intercalated with bromine in our laboratory [52]. In these fibres, bromide anion wires are organised at the interstitial sites of double-layer CNTs. Therefore, the separation between CNTs in the hexagonally-packed array was preserved, and CNT alignment and Young's modulus of fibres were unaltered (~ 142 GPa/SG *versus* ~ 131 GPa/SG after intercalation). Bromine intercalation increased room-temperature longitudinal electrical conductivity by a factor of 8.4; however, the gauge factor of CNT/Br fibres decreased dramatically from 26 to 1.5.

Figure 5. Change in conductance and piezoresistive gauge factor with the amount of residual dopant in LC-spun CNT fibres: undoped fibres demonstrate high gauge factor at the expense of decreased electrical conductance.

3.3 Piezoresistive properties of CNT yarns

While individual CNT fibres are ideal for studying the source and factors controlling piezoresistance, their small diameter (typically, 10-20 μm) makes them impractical for most envisaged applications, for example, for large-scale composite laminate manufacturing. Instead, yarns of multiple fibres are easier to handle and can, therefore, be integrated into large components either manually [27] or through additive manufacturing [26].

Three commercial CNT yarns were investigated: produced *via* FCCVD synthesis (with different degrees of alignment, and therefore, specific modulus of 25 and 100 GPa/SG) and LC-spun yarn with a specific modulus of 55 GPa/SG. Their SAXS patterns, corresponding azimuthal profiles, and Herman's orientation factors are presented in *Supplementary Information, S15*. As expected, the effects of alignment and dopants were also observed in these macroscopic yarns. The commercial multifilament yarns may demonstrate a non-linear stress-strain behaviour (low-modulus FCCVD Yarn#1) due to a small amount of twist and lack of pre-tension in the yarn, which also manifests in a noisy and low piezoresistive signal at small strains $<0.2\%$. However, the sensitivity increases at higher deformations above 0.4% as more stress is transferred to the CNTs. We also noted that an unspecified dopant (potentially introduced in a post-spin treatment) could diminish the GF of an FCCVD yarn despite its relatively high CNT alignment and structural compaction (FCCVD-based Yarn#2 with $\langle P_2 \rangle$ 0.70). In such cases, low-temperature annealing ($<500\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) can be used for removing any unspecified dopant(s), resulting in GF 4 for annealed (purified) Yarn#2 (*Supplementary Information, S16, S17*).

The highly non-linear dependence of piezoresistance in the tested macroscopic yarns would seem challenging for strain sensing if they are used in dry state. Specifically, relatively low GF at the level of 4 was observed for macroscopic yarns which Herman's orientation factors were close to that of individual CNT fibres. Potential non-homogeneity of stress distribution and non-cooperativity of CNTs straining within the multiple filaments play a significant role in their sensitivity compared to individual CNT fibres. This aspect requires a follow-up study on factors affecting the sensitivity of macro-scale multifilament CNT materials. The CNT tow embedded into the GFRP laminate demonstrated high strain sensitivity (Fig. 2) as a result of the lateral constraints of the surrounding polymer medium. The substantially increased gauge factors were reported for CVD array-spun CNT yarns constrained in cured resin when a polymer matrix prevented their unbundling and CNT sliding upon loading [48], therefore contributing to enhanced load transfer between CNTs [53]. Indeed, our parallel study [27] confirmed that after the introduction into a polymer matrix, a porous yarn with a moderate degree of CNT alignment demonstrated higher linearity at small deformations and GF approaching those of the filament. This indicates that polymer infiltration and compaction of constituent fibres induced by high-pressure consolidation during composite manufacturing significantly improved stress transfer between CNTs in the yarns and, thus, their gauge factor, enabling their use as strain gauges in aerospace-grade CFRP laminates [27].

Table 1 summarises the parameters determined for all the tested groups of fibres and yarns as a guideline for choosing CNT macromaterials. When targeting the strain range under 1% for the health monitoring of structural composites, the *ideal* CNT fibre or yarn should have a high gauge factor and the ability to track deformations within a 0.3 % strain margin, which is attainable through higher structural alignment.

Table 1 - Summary of properties of CNT fibres in this study

Type and source	CNT type	$\langle P_2 \rangle$	Specific tensile modulus, GPa/SG	Dopant type	Piezoresistive gauge factor	Sensitivity factor, a
Fibre, FCCVD	FWCNTs	0.50-0.63	50-110	None	2-9	0.02-0.10
	SWCNT		54-110	Annealed HT	10-25	0.20-0.22
Fibre, LC	DWCNT	0.58-0.76	80-120	Acid	1-2	0.010-0.015
			80-140	Annealed MT	10-16	0.09-0.13
			120-170	Annealed HT	20-31	0.17-0.20

Yarn#1, FCCVD	MWCNT	0.46	25	Unknown	~1	0.07
Yarn#2, FCCVD	N/A	0.69	100	Unknown	<<1	<0.01
Yarn#3, LC	DWCNT	0.72	55	Annealed MT	4.2	0.04
				Annealed MT	4	0.07

HT – annealed at high temperature (1400 °C), MT – annealed at medium temperature (500 °C)

4. Discussion

Piezoresistance of the fibres can be described through a combination of a geometric term and change in conductivity, expressed as:

$$\frac{\Delta R}{R_0} = \epsilon(1 + 2\nu) + \frac{\Delta\rho}{\rho_0} \quad (1)$$

where $\frac{\Delta R}{R_0}$ – change in resistance, ϵ – strain, ν – Poisson’s ratio, $\frac{\Delta\rho}{\rho_0}$ – fractional change in resistivity (derivation provided in *Supplementary Information, S18*).

For the deformations involved in this work (under 1% strain, staying safe in the elastic deformation regime of a CNT fibre), the first term is approximately linear with strain and leads to a gauge factor of 1.6 for a typical Poisson ratio of 0.3. It is known that Poisson’s ratio of CNT yarns can vary depending on the degree of compaction and stretching and may reach 8.0 at 0.03 strain, as has been demonstrated for a CVD-array yarn with 90% porosity [54]. However, such a change in Poisson’s ratio is less pronounced for yarns with a more compacted and less porous structure, especially when a CNT yarn is laterally constrained in a polymer. We do not expect noticeable Poisson’s effect on the piezoresistive properties of highly aligned LC-spun yarns with minimised porosity and typical density of close to 2 g/cm³. If one assumes the CNT fibre’s resistance would happen primarily due to the geometric effect, the estimated gauge factor of 1.6 would be too small compared to the experimentally found values of GF, as high as 31, shown in Figure 4 and Table 1. This confirms that CNT fibre piezoresistance is dominated by changes in the intrinsic resistivity of the material. The Poisson’s ratio could also take a different value once the CNT fibre is embedded in a polymer matrix, but nevertheless, still lower than the change in intrinsic resistivity, particularly considering the increase in effective modulus upon polymer ingress [53].

From the data in Figure 4, we find that GF increases with increasing fibre modulus, such that for a family of fibres with identical chemical composition:

$$GF \equiv \frac{\Delta R}{R_0} / \epsilon = \alpha E_f \quad (2)$$

where E_f is the fibre modulus and α is constant (here, a sensitivity factor) that incorporates specificities of the material. As shown in Table 1, for individual FCCVD fibres α is 0.02-0.10, whereas for dopant-free LC fibres α is 0.17-0.22.

Equation 2 can be re-expressed as:

$$\frac{\Delta R}{R_0} = \alpha \sigma_f \quad (3)$$

for CNT fibres with a uniform stress distribution along the fibre length, as is assumed for FCCVD [17] and LC fibres [50] in Figure 4, the average axial stress in the CNTs is equivalent to the macroscopic stress in the fibres and thus:

$$\frac{\Delta R}{R_0} = \alpha \langle \sigma_{CNT} \rangle \quad (4)$$

This simple equation is relevant because it predicts a linear dependence of the macroscopic resistance change on the strain of the CNTs. Note that because of their high modulus, the strain in the CNTs is small, of the order of:

$$\epsilon_{CNT} \approx \epsilon_{fibre} \frac{E_{fibre}}{E_{CNT}} \approx 0.1 \epsilon_{fibre} < 0.005$$

The ultimate goal would be to relate the macroscopic piezoresistive behaviour to the electronic structure of individual CNTs. We take a qualitative step in that direction by analysing the results described above in light of the current understanding of piezoresistance of *individual* CNTs and transport in *macroscopic* CNT fibres.

Piezoresistance has been simulated in individual SWCNTs [55] and experimentally tested through deflection with an AFM tip [56]. Piezoresistance is found only in non-metallic SWCNTs, with an exponential dependence on strain and positive and negative GFs depending on n, m indices due to band gap opening or closing, respectively. However, the opening of a bandgap is unlikely to be the predominant piezoresistance mechanism in *macroscopic* CNT fibre systems. FCCVD aerogel-spun fibres are made of few-layer CNTs, and one of the LC materials is made of DWCNTs. Given the distribution of chiral angles in fibre, the CNTs with positive and negative GFs could cancel out and suppress macroscopic piezoresistance.

In macroscopic fibres of aligned CNTs, electrical conduction is thought to happen through heterogeneous transport between metallic regions separated by conduction barriers, which consist of junctions between CNTs, CNT defects and shape deformations [57,58]. Temperature-dependent resistance measurements show a convex line shape from the combination of metallic-like and semiconducting-like components, often described by the fluctuation-induced tunnelling model

[59]. A higher crystallinity of CNTs, higher degree of alignment and presence of dopants reduce the contribution of the semiconducting term, decreasing overall resistance and lowering the crossover temperature.

The results shown above demonstrate that the gauge factor is maximised when large stress is transferred to the CNTs but that the gauge factor is reduced upon doping by intercalation. Thus, we conclude that piezoresistance in CNT fibres is dominated by the semiconducting-like barrier resistance in the material, and as it is suppressed through intercalation, the magnitude of the GF is decreased. Probably for a similar reason, namely, its effect on transverse resistance, intercalation of highly graphitised carbon fibres has also been observed to decrease longitudinal piezoresistance [60].

It is unclear how the internal conduction barriers develop as a macroscopic strain is applied to the fibre. We hypothesise that an important contribution is from the inherently heterogeneous deformation of CNTs in a fibre, similar to the concept of flexoelectricity inducing polarisation through strain gradients [61]. Internal stress transfer in the fibre occurs through shear between adjacent nanotubes, such that effectively, each CNT is regarded as surrounded by a matrix of secondary bonds, similar to a nanofiller in a polymer matrix with stress transfer described by shear lag theory [62]. At the fibre strain of 0.2% used here, the axial stress distribution in a CNT would start from zero at the nanotube ends and build up to a maximum along 20% of each end of the nanotube (see *Supplementary Information, S19, S20*). In this view, doping would reduce conduction barriers to heterogeneous transport arising from the inhomogeneous internal stress distribution of the individual CNTs. Intercalants have been shown to reduce the transverse resistance of CNT fibres, which is dominated by CNT junctions [52]. Similarly, their effect on piezoresistance would be to reduce the electrical resistance induced by the axial deformation of CNTs in the fibre network.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The piezoresistive behaviour of a range of individual CNT fibres and multifilament yarns has been studied. The aligned fibres showed a quasi-linear piezoresistive response at tensile stretching and demonstrated a positive change in resistance under axial tension and axial and transverse compression. The dependence of piezoresistive strain sensing capabilities on the CNT alignment in macroscopic ensembles was confirmed by means of X-ray SAXS analysis, and a clear relationship between Young's modulus and the gauge factor was shown. The CNT fibres produced by FCCVD aerogel spinning demonstrated a piezoresistive gauge factor between 2-9, and the undoped fibres spun from liquid crystalline solutions had a gauge factor above 20, tested at strains

<1%. It was also revealed that doping through intercalation is detrimental to piezoresistive strain sensing, proportionally to its effect on initial resistivity.

AUTHOR'S CONTRIBUTION STATEMENT

Anastasiia Mikhailchan: methodology, investigation, data processing, data curation, writing – original draft, writing – review & editing, supervision. **Ángel Víctor Labordet Álvarez:** methodology, investigation, validation, data processing, review & editing. **Moisés Zarzoso:** investigation, data processing, review & editing. **Carlos González:** supervision, funding acquisition. **Juan J. Vilatela:** conceptualization, writing – original draft, writing – review & editing, supervision, funding acquisition.

DECLARATION OF COMPETING INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This work has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101007022 (DOMMINIO) and the UNIYARNS ERC-CoG grant (101045394). The authors are grateful to Luis Arevalo for his help with the CNT synthesis and to Carlos Sánchez Gaztelumendi for the preparation and testing of composite samples. SAXS experiments were performed at NCD-SWEET beamline at ALBA synchrotron with cooperation of ALBA staff, the authors are thankful for Marc Malfois and Juan Carlos Martínez for their technical help.

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <http://...>

REFERENCES

- [1] N. Lu, C. Lu, S. Yang, J. Rogers, Highly sensitive skin-mountable strain gauges based entirely on elastomers, *Adv. Funct. Mater.* 22 (2012). <https://doi.org/10.1002/adfm.201200498>.
- [2] P.K. Pramanik, D. Khastgir, S.K. De, T.N. Saha, Pressure-sensitive electrically conductive nitrile rubber composites filled with particulate carbon black and short carbon fibre, *J. Mater. Sci.* 25 (1990). <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF00582450>.
- [3] M. Knite, V. Teteris, A. Kiploka, J. Kaupuzs, Polyisoprene-carbon black nanocomposites as tensile strain and pressure sensor materials, in: *Sensors Actuators, A Phys.*, 2004. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sna.2003.08.006>.
- [4] P. Ahuja, S.K. Ujjain, K. Urita, A. Furuse, I. Moriguchi, K. Kaneko, Chemically and mechanically robust SWCNT based strain sensor with monotonous piezoresistive response

- for infrastructure monitoring, *Chem. Eng. J.* 388 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2020.124174>.
- [5] M.H.G. Wichmann, S.T. Buschhorn, J. Gehrman, K. Schulte, Piezoresistive response of epoxy composites with carbon nanoparticles under tensile load, *Phys. Rev. B - Condens. Matter Mater. Phys.* 80 (2009). <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevB.80.245437>.
- [6] G.T. Pham, Y. Bin Park, Z. Liang, C. Zhang, B. Wang, Processing and modeling of conductive thermoplastic/carbon nanotube films for strain sensing, *Compos. Part B Eng.* 39 (2008). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compositesb.2007.02.024>.
- [7] Q. Zheng, J. hun Lee, X. Shen, X. Chen, J.K. Kim, Graphene-based wearable piezoresistive physical sensors, *Mater. Today.* 36 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mattod.2019.12.004>.
- [8] S. Yu, X. Wang, H. Xiang, L. Zhu, M. Tebyetekerwa, M. Zhu, Superior piezoresistive strain sensing behaviors of carbon nanotubes in one-dimensional polymer fiber structure, *Carbon N. Y.* 140 (2018). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.carbon.2018.08.028>.
- [9] S. Zhao, J. Li, D. Cao, Y. Gao, W. Huang, G. Zhang, R. Sun, C.P. Wong, Percolation threshold-inspired design of hierarchical multiscale hybrid architectures based on carbon nanotubes and silver nanoparticles for stretchable and printable electronics, *J. Mater. Chem. C.* 4 (2016). <https://doi.org/10.1039/c6tc01728b>.
- [10] H. Qin, S. Ding, A. Ashour, Q. Zheng, B. Han, Revolutionizing infrastructure: The evolving landscape of electricity-based multifunctional concrete from concept to practice, *Prog. Mater. Sci.* 145 (2024) 101310. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pmatsci.2024.101310>.
- [11] A. Mikhilchan, A. Pendashteh, J.J. Vilatela, Properties, applications and industrialization of carbon nanotube materials from hydrocarbons cracking, in: *Adv. Chem. Eng.*, 2023. <https://doi.org/10.1016/bs.ache.2023.07.001>.
- [12] J. Di, X. Zhang, Z. Yong, Y. Zhang, D. Li, R. Li, Q. Li, Carbon-Nanotube Fibers for Wearable Devices and Smart Textiles, *Adv. Mater.* 28 (2016) 10529–10538. <https://doi.org/10.1002/adma.201601186>.
- [13] C.D. Fay, N. Mannering, A. Jeiranikhameneh, F. Mokhtari, J. Foroughi, R.H. Baughman, P.F.M. Choong, G.G. Wallace, Wearable Carbon Nanotube-Spandex Textile Yarns for Knee Flexion Monitoring, *Adv. Sens. Res.* 2 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1002/adsr.202200021>.
- [14] L. Dong, M. Ren, Y. Wang, G. Wang, S. Zhang, X. Wei, J. He, B. Cui, Y. Zhao, P. Xu, X. Wang, J. Di, Q. Li, Artificial neuromuscular fibers by multilayered coaxial integration with dynamic adaption, *Sci. Adv.* 8 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1126/sciadv.abq7703>.
- [15] X. Hu, X. Bao, M. Zhang, S. Fang, K. Liu, J. Wang, R. Liu, S.H. Kim, R.H. Baughman, J. Ding, Recent Advances in Carbon Nanotube-Based Energy Harvesting Technologies, *Adv.*

- Mater. 35 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1002/adma.202303035>.
- [16] T.J. Mun, J.H. Moon, J.W. Park, R.H. Baughman, S.J. Kim, Environment-Adaptable Rotational Energy Harvesters Based on Nylon-core Coiled Carbon Nanotube Yarns, *Small Methods*. 7 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1002/smt.202300526>.
- [17] J.C. Fernández-Toribio, B. Alemán, Á. Ridruejo, J.J. Vilatela, Tensile properties of carbon nanotube fibres described by the fibrillar crystallite model, *Carbon N. Y.* 133 (2018) 44–52. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.carbon.2018.03.006>.
- [18] J.-W. Kim, J.M. Gardner, G. Sauti, R.A. Wincheski, B.D. Jensen, K.E. Wise, E.J. Siochi, Multi-scale hierarchical carbon nanotube fiber reinforced composites towards enhancement of axial/transverse strength and fracture toughness, *Compos. Part A Appl. Sci. Manuf.* 167 (2023) 107449. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compositesa.2023.107449>.
- [19] C.E. Evers, B. Vondrasek, C.N. Jolowsky, J.G. Park, M.W. Czabaj, B.E. Ku, K.R. Thagard, G.M. Odegard, Z. Liang, Scalable High Tensile Modulus Composite Laminates Using Continuous Carbon Nanotube Yarns for Aerospace Applications, *ACS Appl. Nano Mater.* 6 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsanm.3c01266>.
- [20] G. Gardiner, Structural health monitoring: Decades of demos build confidence, *Compos. World*. (2015). <https://www.compositesworld.com/articles/structural-health-monitoring-decades-of-demonstrations-build-confidence-in-local-shm>.
- [21] G. Gardiner, Structural health monitoring: NDT-integrated aerostructures, *Compos. World*. (2015). <https://www.compositesworld.com/articles/structural-health-monitoring-ndt-integrated-aerostructures-enter-service>.
- [22] J.L. Abot, Structural Health Monitoring Using Carbon Nanotube Yarns: Sensing Concept and Applications in Composites, in: 2017. <https://doi.org/10.3390/proceedings1080852>.
- [23] J.M. Gardner, G. Sauti, J.W. Kim, R.J. Cano, R.A. Wincheski, C.J. Stelter, B.W. Grimsley, D.C. Working, E.J. Siochi, 3-D printing of multifunctional carbon nanotube yarn reinforced components, *Addit. Manuf.* (2016). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.addma.2016.06.008>.
- [24] D. Vijayakumar, D. Lindley, 3D printing polymeric parts reinforced with carbon nanotube yarn, in: *Nanotub. Superfiber Mater. Sci. Manuf. Commer.*, 2019. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-812667-7.00009-4>.
- [25] A. Mikhanchan, T.E. Tay, A.M. Banas, K. Banas, M.B.H. Breese, A.M. Borkowska, M. Nowakowski, W.M. Kwiatek, C. Paluszkiwicz, Development of continuous CNT fibre-reinforced PMMA filaments for additive manufacturing: A case study by AFM-IR nanoscale imaging, *Mater. Lett.* (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matlet.2019.127182>.
- [26] B. Wincheski, G. Sauti, J. Gardner, E.J. Siochi, Structural Health Monitoring with Carbon Nanotube and Graphene Sensors, in: *ASNT Res. Symp. 2020, NTRS - NASA technical*

- Reports Server, 2020. <https://ntrs.nasa.gov/citations/20200004088>.
- [27] M. Zarzoso, A. Mikhailchan, D. Mocerino, P. Romero, R. Losada, J.J. Vilatela, C. González, Strain sensing of structural composites by integrated piezoresistive CNT yarn sensors, *Compos. Part B Eng.* (n.d.).
- [28] J.L. Abot, T. Alesh, K. Belay, Strain dependence of electrical resistance in carbon nanotube yarns, *Carbon N. Y.* 70 (2014). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.carbon.2013.12.077>.
- [29] H. Zhao, Y. Zhang, P.D. Bradford, Q. Zhou, Q. Jia, F.-G. Yuan, Y. Zhu, Carbon nanotube yarn strain sensors, *Nanotechnology.* 21 (2010) 305502. <https://doi.org/10.1088/0957-4484/21/30/305502>.
- [30] J.C. Anike, K. Belay, J.L. Abot, Piezoresistive response of carbon nanotube yarns under tension: Parametric effects and phenomenology, *Xinxing Tan Cailiao/New Carbon Mater.* 33 (2018). [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1872-5805\(18\)60331-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1872-5805(18)60331-2).
- [31] N. Mallik, M.J. Schulz, V.N. Shanov, D. Hurd, S. Chakraborty, C. Jayasinghe, J. Abot, A. Song, Study on carbon nano-tube spun thread as piezoresistive sensor element, in: *Adv. Mater. Res.*, 2009. <https://doi.org/10.4028/www.scientific.net/AMR.67.155>.
- [32] A. Lekawa-Raus, K.K.K. Koziol, A.H. Windle, Piezoresistive effect in carbon nanotube fibers, *ACS Nano.* 8 (2014). <https://doi.org/10.1021/nn503596f>.
- [33] E. Caffrey, J.R. Garcia, D. O'Suilleabhain, C. Gabbett, T. Carey, J.N. Coleman, Quantifying the Piezoresistive Mechanism in High-Performance Printed Graphene Strain Sensors, *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces.* 14 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsami.1c21623>.
- [34] C.S. Boland, U. Khan, G. Ryan, S. Barwich, R. Charifou, A. Harvey, C. Backes, Z. Li, M.S. Ferreira, M.E. Möbius, R.J. Young, J.N. Coleman, Sensitive electromechanical sensors using viscoelastic graphene-polymer nanocomposites, *Science (80-.).* 354 (2016). <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aag2879>.
- [35] T. Zhai, D. Li, G. Fei, H. Xia, Piezoresistive and compression resistance relaxation behavior of water blown carbon nanotube/polyurethane composite foam, *Compos. Part A Appl. Sci. Manuf.* 72 (2015). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compositesa.2015.02.003>.
- [36] N. Hu, Y. Karube, M. Arai, T. Watanabe, C. Yan, Y. Li, Y. Liu, H. Fukunaga, Investigation on sensitivity of a polymer/carbon nanotube composite strain sensor, *Carbon N. Y.* 48 (2010). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.carbon.2009.10.012>.
- [37] A. Mikhailchan, M. Vila, L. Arévalo, J.J. Vilatela, Simultaneous improvements in conversion and properties of molecularly controlled CNT fibres, *Carbon N. Y.* 179 (2021) 417–424. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.carbon.2021.04.033>.
- [38] M. Vazquez-Puffleau, R. Fernandez Torres, L. Arevalo, N. Abomailek, J.J. Vilatela, Mapping carbon nanotube aspect ratio, concentration and spinning in FCCVD synthesis

- controlled by sulphur, *Carbon Trends*. 15 (2024) 100355. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cartre.2024.100355>.
- [39] L.W. Taylor, O.S. Dewey, R.J. Headrick, N. Komatsu, N.M. Peraca, G. Wehmeyer, J. Kono, M. Pasquali, Improved properties, increased production, and the path to broad adoption of carbon nanotube fibers, *Carbon N. Y.* 171 (2021) 689–694. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.carbon.2020.07.058>.
- [40] J.C. Stallard, W. Tan, F.R. Smail, T.S. Gspann, A.M. Boies, N.A. Fleck, The mechanical and electrical properties of direct-spun carbon nanotube mats, *Extrem. Mech. Lett.* 21 (2018) 65–75. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eml.2018.03.003>.
- [41] H. Xu, L. Chen, L. Hu, N. Zhitenev, Contact resistance of flexible, transparent carbon nanotube films with metals, *Appl. Phys. Lett.* 97 (2010). <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.3496465>.
- [42] M. Basham, J. Filik, M.T. Wharmby, P.C.Y. Chang, B. El Kassaby, M. Gerring, J. Aishima, K. Levik, B.C.A. Pulford, I. Sikharulidze, D. Sneddon, M. Webber, S.S. Dhesi, F. Maccherozzi, O. Svensson, S. Brockhauser, G. Náray, A.W. Ashton, IUCr, Data Analysis WorkbeNch (DAWN), *Urn:Issn:1600-5775*. 22 (2015) 853–858. <https://doi.org/10.1107/S1600577515002283>.
- [43] J.C. Fernández-Toribio, A. Mikhalchan, C. Santos, Á. Ridruejo, J.J. Vilatela, Understanding cooperative loading in carbon nanotube fibres through in-situ structural studies during stretching, *Carbon N. Y.* 156 (2020) 430–437. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.CARBON.2019.09.070>.
- [44] A. Mikhalchan, C. Madrona, L. Arévalo, M. Malfois, J.J. Vilatela, Improved alignment and stress transfer in CNT fibre fabrics studied by in situ X-ray and Raman during wet-drawing, *Carbon N. Y.* 197 (2022) 368–377. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.carbon.2022.06.045>.
- [45] S.N. Lawandy, A.A. Abd-ElMaged, S.F. Halim, Using strain deformation measurements to study the mechanical behaviour of butyl/organo-modified nanoclay composites, *Int. J. Eng. Sci. Innov. Technol.* 3 (2014) 68–76.
- [46] I. Garcia Guerra, T. Tayyarian, O. Rodríguez-Uicab, J.L. Abot, Piezoresistive Response of Carbon Nanotube Yarn Monofilament Composites under Axial Compression, *C-Journal Carbon Res.* 9 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.3390/c9040089>.
- [47] D.D.L. Chung, A critical review of piezoresistivity and its application in electrical-resistance-based strain sensing, *J. Mater. Sci.* 55 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10853-020-05099-z>.
- [48] J. Anike, H. Le, G. Brodeur, M. Kadavan, J. Abot, Piezoresistive Response of Integrated CNT Yarns under Compression and Tension: The Effect of Lateral Constraint, *C.* 3 (2017). <https://doi.org/10.3390/c3020014>.

- [49] S. Ding, X. Wang, L. Qiu, Y.Q. Ni, X. Dong, Y. Cui, A. Ashour, B. Han, J. Ou, Self-Sensing Cementitious Composites with Hierarchical Carbon Fiber-Carbon Nanotube Composite Fillers for Crack Development Monitoring of a Maglev Girder, *Small*. 19 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1002/smll.202206258>.
- [50] D. Lee, S.G. Kim, S. Hong, C. Madrona, Y. Oh, M. Park, N. Komatsu, L.W. Taylor, B. Chung, J. Kim, J.Y. Hwang, J. Yu, D.S. Lee, H.S. Jeong, N.H. You, N.D. Kim, D.-Y. Kim, H.S. Lee, K.-H. Lee, J. Kono, G. Wehmeyer, M. Pasquali, J.J. Vilatela, S. Ryu, B.-C. Ku, Ultrahigh strength, modulus, and conductivity of graphitic fibers by macromolecular coalescence, *Sci. Adv.* 8 (2022) eabn0939. <https://doi.org/10.1126/sciadv.abn0939>.
- [51] R.J. Headrick, D.E. Tsentelovich, J. Berdegué, E.A. Bengio, L. Liberman, O. Kleinerman, M.S. Lucas, Y. Talmon, M. Pasquali, Structure–Property Relations in Carbon Nanotube Fibers by Downscaling Solution Processing, *Adv. Mater.* 30 (2018). <https://doi.org/10.1002/adma.201704482>.
- [52] C. Madrona, S. Hong, D. Lee, J. García-Pérez, J.M. Guevara-Vela, R.B. Gavito, A. Mikhailchian, J. Llorca, B.-C. Ku, D. Granados, J.Y. Hwang, J.J. Vilatela, Continuous intercalation compound fibers of bromine wires and aligned CNTs for high-performance conductors, *Carbon* N. Y. 204 (2023) 211–218. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.carbon.2022.12.041>.
- [53] B. Mas, A. Monreal-Bernal, H. Yue, H. Zhang, J.J. Vilatela, Understanding the enhancement of Young’s modulus of macroscopic carbon nanotube fibers after polymer infiltration, in: *AIP Conf. Proc.*, 2019. <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.5084886>.
- [54] M. Miao, J. McDonnell, L. Vuckovic, S.C. Hawkins, Poisson’s ratio and porosity of carbon nanotube dry-spun yarns, *Carbon* N. Y. 48 (2010). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.carbon.2010.04.009>.
- [55] L. Yang, J. Han, Electronic structure of deformed carbon nanotubes, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* 85 (2000). <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevLett.85.154>.
- [56] C. Stampfer, T. Helbling, A. Jungen, C. Hierold, Piezoresistance of single-walled carbon nanotubes, in: *TRANSDUCERS EUROSENSORS ’07 - 4th Int. Conf. Solid-State Sensors, Actuators Microsystems*, 2007. <https://doi.org/10.1109/SENSOR.2007.4300445>.
- [57] A. Bezryadin, A.R.M. Verschueren, S.J. Tans, C. Dekker, Multiprobe transport experiments on individual single-wall carbon nanotubes, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* 80 (1998). <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevLett.80.4036>.
- [58] C.L. Kane, E.J. Mele, Size, shape, and low energy electronic structure of carbon nanotubes, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* 78 (1997). <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevLett.78.1932>.
- [59] J.S. Bulmer, A. Kaniyoor, J.A. Elliott, A Meta-Analysis of Conductive and Strong Carbon

- Nanotube Materials, Adv. Mater. 33 (2021) 2008432.
<https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1002/adma.202008432>.
- [60] S. Błazewicz, B. Patalita, P. Touzain, Study of piezoresistance effect in carbon fibers, Carbon N. Y. 35 (1997). [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0008-6223\(97\)00120-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0008-6223(97)00120-6).
- [61] A. Abdollahi, F. Vásquez-Sancho, G. Catalan, Piezoelectric Mimicry of Flexoelectricity, Phys. Rev. Lett. 121 (2018). <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevLett.121.205502>.
- [62] Z. Li, L. Deng, I.A. Kinloch, R.J. Young, Raman spectroscopy of carbon materials and their composites: Graphene, nanotubes and fibres, Prog. Mater. Sci. 135 (2023) 101089. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pmatsci.2023.101089>.

The effects of CNT type, alignment and dopants on piezoresistance in CNT fibres

Anastasiia Mikhalchan,^a Ángel Víctor Labordet Álvarez,^a Moisés Zarzoso,^{a,b} Carlos González,^{a,b*}

Juan J. Vilatela^{a*}

^a IMDEA Materials Institute, 28906 Getafe, Madrid, Spain

^b Universidad Politécnica de Madrid, E.T.S. de Ingenieros de Caminos, 28040 Madrid, Spain

* Corresponding author. IMDEA Materials Institute, 28906 Getafe, Madrid, Spain

E-mail address: juanjose.vilatela@imdea.org (J. J. Vilatela), Carlos Gonzalez carlosdaniel.gonzalez@imdea.org

Fig. S1. Commercial CNT yarns.

Fig. S2. Contact resistance by the Transfer Length Measurement method.

Fig. S3. Examples of 2-probe and 4-probe electrical measurements.

S4. R_0 values for the different groups of tested CNT fibres

CNT material	Length, mm	R_0 range, Ohm
LC fibres, DWCNT as-produced	20	15 - 18
LC fibres, DWCNT annealed HT	20	90 - 100
FCCVD fibres, SWCNT	20	1700 - 2770
FCCVD fibres, MWCNT	20	850 - 2250
FCCVD fibres, FWCNT	20	350 - 1700
Yarn #1, FCCVD, as-produced	50	~20
Yarn #2, FCCVD, as-produced	50	~2.5
Yarn #3, LC, annealed MT	50	~2.3

Fig. S5. Stability of the electrical resistance of the CNT tow embedded in a GFRP coupon.

The following zones are shown: **i)** connecting and positioning the electrical setup (crocodile clamps); **ii)** the sample was kept on the desk to stabilize the electrical signal; **iii)** change in the signal due to the clamping of the sample in the grips of the Instron machine imposing significant pressure to hold the sample; **iv)** stable electrical signal while the sample was kept in the grips.

Fig. S6. Stability of the embedded electrical contacts in GFRP sample.

Fig. S7. Stability of the electrical contacts made with a CNT yarn.

Fig. S8. Schematic overview and the photo of the measurement setup in Favimat machine.

Fig. S9. Example of tensile and piezoresistive data for a LC-spun CNT fibre.

Fig. S10. Behaviour of FCCVD- and LC-spun CNT fibres.

Fig. S11. Relative resistance change with applied tensile stress.

Fig. S12. Hysteresis in CNT fibres and yarn.

Fig. S13. Repeatability of the relative change in resistance in cycling.

S14. Orientation parameters.

The Herman's orientation factor is commonly used to compare degree of alignment in fibres and other materials with fibre symmetry. It takes values of 0 for random alignment, -0.5 for perfect perpendicular alignment, and 1 for perfect parallel alignment. Referred to as $\langle P_2 \rangle$, it is the second moment of orientation distribution expanded as Legendre polynomials.

$$\langle P_2 \rangle = \frac{1}{2} (3 \langle \cos^2 \beta \rangle)$$

$$\langle \cos^2 \beta \rangle = \frac{\int_0^\pi I(\beta) \cos^2 \beta \sin \beta d\beta}{\int_0^\pi I(\beta) \sin \beta d\beta}$$

For this work, $I(\beta)$ is obtained the azimuthal intensity profile from 2D SAXS. Because the main WAXS/SAXS reflections in CNT fibres are orthogonal to the CNT axis, i.e. on the equator, we shift the intensity distribution by a factor of $\pi/2$

$$I(\beta) = I_{SAXS}(\theta + \pi/2)$$

When using the uniform stress model, which relates the orientation of CNTs to the bulk modulus (and in this work piezoresistance), the relevant factor is instead

$$\langle \cos^2 \theta \rangle = \frac{\int_0^\pi I_{SAXS}(\theta) \cos^2 \theta \sin \theta d\theta}{\int_0^\pi I_{SAXS}(\theta) \sin \theta d\theta}$$

Fig. S15. SAXS azimuthal profiles for A) yarn #1 (FCCVD), B) yarn #2 (FCCVD), and C) yarn #3 (LC).

Fig. S16. TGA test showing ~1% wt fraction of the component decomposed at ~163 °C.

Fig. S17. Piezoresistive behaviour and corresponding change in resistance versus tensile strain for the yarn #2 (FCCVD) as-supplied (A, B) and annealed in N₂ atmosphere (C, D).

S18. Piezoresistance

Fibre resistance is expressed as

$$R = \frac{\rho L}{\pi r^2} \quad (1)$$

The change upon deformation is

$$\begin{aligned} dR &= \frac{\partial R}{\partial \rho} d\rho + \frac{\partial R}{\partial r} dr + \frac{\partial R}{\partial L} dL \\ dR &= \frac{L}{\pi r^2} d\rho - \frac{2\rho L}{\pi r^3} dr + \frac{\rho}{\pi r^2} dL \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

The initial resistance is given by

$$R_0 = \frac{\rho_0 L_0}{\pi r_0^2} \quad (3)$$

Substituting (3) in (2)

$$\frac{dR}{R_0} = \frac{\pi r_0^2}{\rho_0 L_0} \left(\frac{L}{\pi r^2} d\rho - \frac{2\rho L}{\pi r^3} dr + \frac{\rho}{\pi r^2} dL \right) \quad (4)$$

For small deformations, we consider

$$\rho \approx \rho_0, \quad r \approx r_0, \quad l \approx l_0$$

And therefore

$$\frac{dR}{R_0} = \frac{d\rho}{\rho_0} - 2 \frac{dr}{r} + \frac{dL}{L} \quad (5)$$

Recalling the definition of Poisson ratio:

$$\nu \equiv -\frac{dr}{r} \bigg/ \frac{dL}{L} = \frac{dr}{r} / \epsilon$$

Leads to the simplified expression for piezoresistance

$$\frac{dR}{R_0} = \frac{d\rho}{\rho_0} + \epsilon(2\nu + 1) \quad (6)$$

S19. Stress distribution along a CNT in a perfectly aligned fibre.

The stress along a tube is calculated assuming the nanotube surrounded by other CNTs can be considered as embedded in a matrix of secondary bonds that transfer stress by shear. Following the shear lag model, the stress at a position x from the middle of the tube is given by

$$\sigma_{bundle}(x/l) = e_c \epsilon \left[1 - \frac{\cosh(2\mu s x/l)}{\cosh(\mu s)} \right], \text{ for } 0 \leq |x| \leq \frac{1}{2}L$$

$$\mu = \sqrt{\frac{4g}{c e_c}}$$

$$c = \ln\left(\frac{2\pi}{\sqrt{3}V_f}\right)$$

With L the CNT length, e_c the axial modulus = 1000GPa, ϵ the fibre deformation $\epsilon = 0.2\%$, s the aspect ratio of the load-bearing element $s = 100$, g the shear modulus $g = 9.3$ GPa, and V_f the volume fraction $V_f = 0.86$.

Fig. S20. Axial stress distribution along a CNT under the 0.2% deformation used to measure piezoresistance and gauge factor in this work.